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Green synthesis of Ceriumoxide Nanoparticles using *Bacopa monnieri* Leaf Extract - *In vitro* Antioxidant Activity

Mamatha Madhugiri Gopinath¹, Sumreen Sultana¹,
Shital Manohar Puneekar¹, M B Nivedika¹, Ravikiran Tekupalli^{1*}

¹ Department of Microbiology and Biotechnology, Bangalore University, Bengaluru, 560056, India

Abstract

Objectives: Cerium oxide nanoparticles were synthesized by a rapid green method using an aqueous leaf extract of *Bacopa monnieri* to investigate its antioxidant activity. **Methods:** Cerium oxide nanoparticles (CeO₂ NPs) were synthesized using *Bacopa monnieri* leaf extract as a stabilizing agent by solution combustion method. Characterization techniques like FTIR, PXRD, SEM-EDAX, HR-TEM, UV-visible, and Raman spectroscopy confirmed the synthesized NPs. The antioxidant capacity was assessed by *in vitro* Hydroxyl radical scavenging assay. **Findings:** The biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs possess tiny spherical shapes and sizes ranging from 5-50nm, and the average particle size is 27 nm as measured by HR-TEM. XRD and Raman confirm the nanoparticle's polycrystalline nature and face-centered cubic fluorite structure with maximum UV-visible absorbance at λ_{max} 301.2nm. The biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs exhibited better scavenging activity than Vitamin C. However, further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies must be warranted to explore its mechanism and therapeutic potential. **Novelty:** To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report involving the green synthesis of cerium oxide nanoparticles using *Bacopa monnieri* leaf extract, which exhibited potent hydroxyl radical scavenging activity which can be a promising therapeutic candidate in oxidative stress-related disorders.

Keywords: CeO₂ NPs; Green synthesis; *Bacopa monnieri*; HR-TEM; Hydroxyl radical

1 Introduction

Nanotechnology deals with nanoparticles (NPs) that are atomic or molecular aggregates characterized by a size of less than 100 nm and are key players in modern medicine with applications ranging from bioimaging to therapeutic drugs⁽¹⁾. Among various inorganic NPs, CeO₂ NPs have received much attention due to their practical applications as catalysts, chemical polishing, fuel cells, and antioxidants in biological systems⁽²⁾.

Recently, cerium oxide nanoparticles possessing anti-oxidative properties have emerged as potential therapeutic agents in various fields including nanomedicine⁽³⁾.

Cerium is a member of the lanthanide series with a fluorite structure and rare earth oxide material, as it is most abundant in the earth's crust, among other elements⁽⁴⁾. It also possesses a unique electronic configuration due to the large surface area to volume ratio that creates oxygen defects on its surface⁽⁵⁾. Many unique features are mainly linked with the co-existence of a dual oxidation Ce^{4+} and Ce^{3+} state at the nanoparticle surface, enabling them to act as oxidizing and reducing agents⁽⁶⁾. Recent studies reported CeO_2 NPs mimetic superoxide dismutase and catalase activity and have emerged as a fascinating material in biological fields⁽⁷⁾.

Typically, nanoparticles are synthesized from various chemical and physical methods, which are costly, inefficient, and energy-intensive, and also utilize toxic chemicals that lead to hazardous waste production in the environment^(8,9). Nowadays, scientists are adapting the principles of green chemistry for the synthesis of nanoparticles as they are safe and non-toxic⁽¹⁰⁾. Plants are considered as the most potential agent for the green synthesis due to their easy availability, safe and ecofriendly nature. Plants are rich source of secondary metabolites such as polyphenols, alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids which act as stabilizing and capping agents⁽¹¹⁾.

Plant-mediated nanoparticle synthesis is considered eco-friendly, biocompatible, and possesses a wide variety of secondary metabolites⁽¹²⁾. Different plant extracts have been used for the synthesis of CeO_2 NPs, including *Origanum majorana*. L⁽¹³⁾, *Ceratonia siliqua*. L⁽¹⁴⁾, *Moringa oleifera*⁽¹⁵⁾, *Jatropha curcus*⁽¹⁶⁾, and *Acorus calamus*⁽¹⁷⁾. The phytochemicals wrap effectively on NP's surface, thus showing higher catalytic reactivity and greater surface area, which play an essential role in adsorbing and neutralizing free radicals⁽¹⁸⁾. Indian traditional medicine uses various herbs to treat several diseases. One such medicinal plant is *Bacopa monnieri* (*B. monnieri*), which belongs to Plantaginaceae. It is commonly known as Bramhi or Medha rasayanas and is used in Ayurveda as a memory enhancer, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antiepileptic, antidiarrhoeal, anticancer, and sedative agent⁽¹⁹⁾. It contains alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, and distinctive saponins called "bacosides"⁽²⁰⁾.

Numerous studies have reported that green synthesized CeO_2 NPs exhibits varying antioxidant activity. The studies of Yulizar et al.,⁽²¹⁾ showed that CeO_2 NPs synthesized by *Datura metel* L. leaf extract exhibited considerable free radical scavenging activity (16.61%). Whereas, green synthesized CeO_2 NPs from different plant extract reported the highest antioxidant activity at 500 μ g/mL^(22,23). Therefore, the present study aimed to biosynthesize CeO_2 NPs, using *B. monnieri* leaf extract as a reducing agent, and to evaluate its antioxidant activity.

2 Methodology

2.1 Chemicals and reagents

Cerium nitrate hexahydrate ($Ce(NO_3)_3 \cdot 6H_2O$), Deoxy-2-ribose, and Thiobarbituric acid were obtained from Sigma (St. Louis, MO, USA). All organic solvents were of spectral grade, and general chemicals were of analytical quality and were purchased from local companies.

2.2 Collection of plant material

The leaves of *B. monnieri* were collected from local market in Bangalore. The authentication of plant material (RRCBI-19971) was done in the department of Botany, Central Ayurveda Research Institute, Bangalore.

2.3 Preparation of plant extracts

The fresh leaves of *B. monnieri* were washed thoroughly under running tap water and shade dried at room temperature. The dried leaves were finely powdered using a blender. The aqueous leaf extract was prepared following the procedure⁽²⁴⁾. Briefly, the powdered samples were soaked in distilled water for about 24hrs. The extract was filtered through Whatman filter paper no-1, and the filtrate was collected, lyophilized and stored at -20 °C until further use.

2.4 Biochemical assays of aqueous leaf extract

2.4.1 Determination of phenol content

The phenol content was determined in the extract using the method⁽²⁵⁾. Appropriate extract dilutions were mixed with 2.5 mL of 10 % Folin-Ciocalteau's reagent (v/v) and neutralized with 2.0 mL of 7.5 % sodium carbonate. The reaction mixture was incubated for 40 min at 45 °C, and the absorbance was measured at 765 nm in the spectrophotometer. The total phenol content was calculated using gallic acid as standard.

2.4.2 Determination of flavonoid content

The flavonoid content of the extract was determined according to the method⁽²⁶⁾. Briefly, 0.5 mL of appropriately diluted sample was mixed with 0.5 ml methanol, 50 μ L of 10 % AlCl₃, 50 μ L of 1 M Potassium acetate, and 1.4 ml water and incubated at RT for 30 minutes. After that, the absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured at 415 nm. The total flavonoids were calculated using quercetin as standard.

2.5 Synthesis of CeO₂ NPs

The CeO₂ NPs were synthesized by solution combustion according to the protocol⁽²⁷⁾. Initially, 0.5g of lyophilized *B. monnieri* aqueous extract was added to 50 ml distilled water and continuously stirred. Then 30ml of aqueous leaf extract was mixed with 0.5g of precursor Ce(NO₃)₃·6H₂O (99.99% pure, 0.036M, pH 3.7) on a magnetic stirrer. Later, the reaction mixture was poured in to porcelain crucible and placed in the pre-heated muffle furnace at 572 \pm 20 °C until nanoparticle formation (around 30min).

2.6 Characterization of CeO₂ NPs

2.6.1 Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR spectroscopy)

The Fourier transform Infrared (FTIR) spectra of the standard and green synthesized CeO₂ NPs were recorded on FTIR Perkin Elmer Spectrometer (Spectrum 1000) By KBr pellet method in the scanning range of 400-4000 cm⁻¹ at 4 cm⁻¹ resolution.

2.6.2 X-ray diffraction (XRD measurement)

X-ray diffractograms of synthesized CeO₂ NPs were obtained with an X-ray diffractometer (Smartlab, Rigaku) using Ni-filtered CuK α radiation (1.2kW, 40kV, 30mA).

2.6.3 Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The surface morphology of the green synthesized CeO₂ NPs was characterized by a scanning electron microscope (TM 3000, Hitachi, Japan). The powdered CeO₂ NP sample was sprinkled on an aluminum stub using double-sided carbon tape. The image was captured in SEM mode at desired magnification.

2.6.4 High resolution-Transmission Electron Microscopy (HR-TEM)

HR-TEM analysis of the green synthesized CeO₂ NPs was carried out by Tecnai G2, F30 FEI, with an accelerating voltage of up to 300 kV and a Spot resolution of 2.0 Å.

2.6.5 UV- Vis spectral analysis

The UV–Vis analysis was performed using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Multiscan GO, Thermo Scientific) and scanning the spectra between 200 and 800 nm at the resolution of 1 nm.

2.6.6 Raman spectroscopy

The synthesized CeO₂ NPs were analyzed using Raman spectroscopy (ID Raman reader) to obtain vibrational modes information. The wavelength of laser light was set at 785 nm and scanned at 200 to 2,000 cm⁻¹.

2.7 Free radical scavenging activity

2.7.1 Hydroxyl radical assay

Hydroxyl radical scavenging assay was determined according to the method⁽²⁸⁾. Briefly, different concentrations of the sample (0.195-50 μ l) were added to a reaction mixture containing 120 μ L of 20mM deoxyribose, 400 μ L of 0.1M phosphate buffer, 40 μ L of 20mM H₂O₂, 40 μ L of 500mM FeSO₄, and the final volume was made up to 800 μ L with distilled water. The reaction mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 30min. After the incubation period, 0.5mL of 2.8% TCA was added to stop the reaction, followed by the addition of 0.4mL of 0.6% TBA solution. The reaction mixtures were subsequently incubated in a boiling water bath for 20min. The absorbance was measured at 532 nm in a spectrophotometer.

$$\text{Scavenging effect (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance (control)} - \text{Absorbance (sample)}}{\text{Absorbance (control)}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, Absorbance (control) = absorbance of the control (reacting mixture without the test sample) and Abs (sample) = absorbance of the mixture with the test sample.

Table 1. Total phenol and flavonoid content *B.monniери* leaves extract

Green synthesized CeO ₂ NPs (30 ml extract volume)	
Total phenols (mg GAE/g extract)	Total flavonoids (mg QE/g extract)
110.64±2.15	92.47±1.79

Values are represented as mean ± S.E (n=3)

3 Results and Discussion

In our study, the aqueous leaf extract of *B. monniери* was used for the green synthesis of CeO₂ NPs. *B. monniери* is a rich source of secondary metabolites such as phenols and flavonoids, which plays a significant role as reducing and stabilizing agents. These metabolites can act as binding molecules around the cerium atoms (Ce³⁺), which help form CeO₂ NPs at 570±20 °C. The total Phenol (TPC) and Flavonoid (TFC) content was estimated. The TPC value was found to be 110.64±2.15mg GAE/g extract, and TFC was found to be 92.47±1.79mg QE/g extract, as represented in Table 1. Our results revealed that phenol content was more than flavonoids which confirms the plausible participation of phenols in the reduction of metal nitrate to metal oxides.

The synthesized NPs were further characterized by FTIR spectroscopy to identify the biomolecules responsible for reducing and stabilizing the cerium oxide nanoparticles. The FTIR spectrum of cerium oxide nanoparticles is shown in Figure 1 a. The spectrum was recorded in the wave number range from 4000-400 cm⁻¹. The bands at 1635.71 and 3375.80 cm⁻¹ represent the OH bend of the water and hydroxyl groups, respectively. The C=C bonds of the aromatic group can be confirmed by the band at 1600.44 cm⁻¹. The intensive band at 1384.23 cm⁻¹ represents the N-O stretch due to the presence of nitrate. The absorption band at 494 cm⁻¹ represents the O-Ce-O stretch which is in accordance with the previous studies⁽²⁹⁾. In addition, the transmittance peaks obtained at 845 and 1062 cm⁻¹ could be attributed to CO₃²⁻ bending vibration and C-O stretching vibration, respectively.

Fig 1. CeO₂ NPs Characterization (a) FTIR (b) UV-vis spectroscopy (inset, bandgap) (c) XRD pattern (d) Raman spectroscopy

Besides, the CeO₂ NPs formation can also portrayed from the UV-Visible absorbance spectrum (Figure 1 b). The UV-vis absorbance spectra were recorded for the nanoparticles against water as blank. A well-defined characteristic peak around

λ_{max} 301.2 nm was observed for the synthesized CeO₂ NPs, possibly due to an electron transition from the valence band to the conductance band. The absorption spectra obtained in the UV spectrometric analysis is very close to the band obtained for CeO₂ NPs, as reported in the previous study⁽³⁰⁾. The optical bandgap energy was calculated using Tauc's relation.

$$\alpha hv = A (hv - E_g)^n \quad (2)$$

where $h\nu$; photon energy, α ; absorption coefficient ($\alpha = 4\pi k / \lambda$, k ; absorption index or absorbance, λ ; the wavelength in nanometer), E_g ; energy band gap, A ; constant, $n = 1/2$ for the allowed direct band gap. The exponent 'n' depends on the type of transition and it may have values 1/2, 2, 3/2 and 3 corresponding to the allowed direct, allowed indirect, forbidden direct and forbidden indirect transitions respectively. The energy bandgap value was determined by extrapolating the straight line (Figure 1 b, inset) and the value found to be around 3.68 eV. The band gap value was found to be lower than the CeO₂ NPs synthesized using Gloriosa superb leaf extract⁽³¹⁾. Further, the synthesized CeO₂ showed an increase in energy band gap compared to the bulk CeO₂ powder ($E_g = 3.19$ eV) which might be due to the quantum confinement in the system.

The crystalline structure of the synthesized CeO₂ NPs was studied using XRD, as shown in Figure 1 c. The sample was scanned from 10°-80° degrees with a scan rate of 2θ min⁻¹. The XRD spectra indicate the pure cubic fluorite structure and polycrystalline nature of the CeO₂ NPs. The high-intensity peaks observed at 28.55°, 33.08°, 47.48°, 56.33°, 59.09°, 69.40°, 76.70°, and 79.07° corresponds to the (111), (200), (220), (311), (222), (400), (331) and (420) crystal planes respectively. The crystal planes were in good accordance with JCPDS No 34-0394 and matched well with the previous XRD studies⁽¹⁶⁾. A characteristic impurity peak was observed, which may be due to an error while sample preparation, and this can be ignored as it is negligible impurity by considering the major phase of the cubic system. Further, the crystallite size and structural parameters such as d-spacing, lattice constant (Å), dislocation density (d) and microstrain (ε) estimated and represented in Table 2.

Table 2. CeO₂ NPs structural parameter data obtained from XRD analysis

CeO ₂ NPs	hkl planes	d-spacing	Lattice parameter (Å) a=b=c	Dislocation density (d) × 10 ¹⁵ (1/m ²)	Microstrain (ε) × 10 ⁻³	Crystallite size (nm)		
30 ml volume	(1,1,1)	(2,0,0)	3.123	2.706	5.409	1.94	2.38	22.67
	(2,2,0)	(3,1,1)	1.913	1.632				
	(2,2,2)	(4,0,0)	1.562	1.353				
	(3,3,1)		1.241					
	(4,2,0)		1.210					

Crystal System: Cubic, Space Group: Fm-3m (225)

Crystallite size was calculated using Debye's Scherrer equation.

$$D = \frac{K\lambda}{\beta \cos\theta} \quad (3)$$

d-spacing was evaluated using the equation

$$n\lambda = 2d \sin\theta \quad (4)$$

Where K is the shape factor, λ is the X-ray wavelength CuK α (1.5406 Å), β is the line broadening at half the maximum intensity (FWHM) in radians, and θ is the Bragg's angle, 'D' is the crystallite size. n is 1 (order of diffraction), d is interplanar spacing or Å. The average crystallite size was found to be 22.67 nm using *B. monnieri* leaf extract. The lattice parameter calculated from the reflection plane (111) for biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs by the below formula

$$a = d_{hkl} \sqrt{h^2 + k^2 + l^2} \quad (5)$$

Where d is the spacing and hkl are the Miller indices. The calculated lattice parameters of biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs a= 0.5409 nm is small which indicates that the *B. monnieri* leaf extract might remain adhered on the surface of CeO₂ instead of comprising into the lattice of CeO₂ NPs. The micro strain (ε) of biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs was calculated by the formula

$$\epsilon = \frac{\beta \cos\theta}{4} \quad (6)$$

A dislocation density (δ) is a crystallographic defect in crystal structure. It was calculated using formula

$$\delta = \frac{1}{D^2} \text{ lines/m}^2 \quad (7)$$

As depicted in Table 2, dislocation density is slightly higher than the pure CeO₂ as reported by the studies⁽³²⁾ which may be due to lesser oxygen vacancy present on the surface of CeO₂ NPs. However, the results of micro strain and dislocation density revealed the good lattice structure for CeO₂ NPs suggesting *B. monnieri* leaf extract can strongly influences the catalytic and electrochemical properties.

The presence of the cubic structure of the synthesized CeO₂ NPs by Raman spectroscopy is shown in Figure 1 d. The strong Raman band observed at 460 cm⁻¹ (F_{2g} mode) is close to the characteristic Raman frequency as reported previously⁽³³⁾. The obtained Raman peak confirms the presence of CeO₂ with cubic crystalline structure ascertained with the XRD result, which can be attributed to the symmetric vibrations of the Ce-O Raman active mode.

The morphological characterization was carried out to understand the size, shape, and surface morphology of CeO₂ NPs. SEM and EDAX profile of CeO₂ NPs is shown in Figure 2 a. The SEM image illustrates that the particles were uniform, tiny spherical, and the size ranges between 5-50nm. The EDAX spectra of synthesized NPs indicate the presence of cerium (77.07%) and oxygen (22.93%) in weight percentage. In contrast, the atomic % of elements Ce and O is 27.73% and 72.27%, respectively. Hence, the EDAX profile indicates the high purity of the synthesized CeO₂ NPs, which corresponds well with the XRD results.

Fig 2. Morphological characterization of biosynthesized CeO₂NPs (a) SEM - EDAX analysis (b) HR-TEM analysis and size distribution histogram (inset, SAED pattern)

The detailed structural analysis of the CeO₂ NPs was characterized by HR-TEM and selected area electron diffraction (SAED). A low-magnification image of the NPs is depicted in Figure 2 b. Most of the particles are spherical, along with a few cubic particles with a mean size of 27 nm. The SAED pattern shows several weak Scherrer rings corresponding to the reflections of the cubic CeO₂ sample. The characterization results reveal that the synthesized CeO₂ NPs had a particle size in the nanoscale with high crystallinity.

Antioxidants are vital to the human body as it protects against oxidative damage by free radicals such as hydroxyl radicals, superoxide radicals, and singlet oxygen⁽³⁴⁾. The hydroxyl [OH·] radical, generated by the Fenton reaction, contains a highly reactive oxygen center. It can bind the nucleotides in DNA and cause strand breakage that leads to mutagenesis, carcinogenesis, and cytotoxicity⁽¹⁴⁾. As cerium is a potent antioxidant, the effectiveness of synthesized CeO₂ NPs was investigated by OH free

radical scavenging activity. The previous studies reported that biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs exhibited hydroxyl scavenging activity at higher concentration of 200 µg/mL and 500 µg/mL^(14,35). In our study, the biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs showed potent dose-dependent OH radical scavenging activity compared to Vitamin C at a lower concentration of 0.195–50 µg/mL (Figure 3). This is possibly due to their explicit physicochemical properties and greater oxygen vacancy on CeO₂ NPs surface⁽³⁶⁾.

Fig 3. Dose dependent Hydroxyl radical scavenging activity of biosynthesized CeO₂NPs. Data represented as mean ± S.E (n=3)

4 Conclusion

CeO₂ NPs were successfully synthesized by an eco-friendly approach using the aqueous leaf extract of *B. monnieri* as a reducing agent leading to the reduction of metal nitrate into metal oxide. The biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs were characterized by techniques such as XRD, FTIR, UV-Vis, SEM and HR-TEM. XRD pattern elucidated the formation of pure cubic fluorite structure and polycrystalline nature. FTIR analysis confirms the presence of functional groups belonging to phytochemicals responsible for bioreduction during CeO₂ NPs formation. Besides, UV-Vis absorption at 301.2nm and Raman spectroscopy at 460 cm⁻¹ revealed characteristic peaks that highly confirm the CeO₂ NPs formation. SEM and HR-TEM analysis revealed the formation of small spherical NPs and the EDAX profile confirms Ce-O elemental purity. The biosynthesized CeO₂ NPs exhibited better hydroxyl radical scavenging activity (65%) compared to vitamin C (60%). Thus, we can conclude that CeO₂ NPs show good antioxidant potential which may be utilized as a novel therapeutic agent in the treatment of oxidative stress-related disorders.

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